

Original Research

Impact of Forward Looking Statement on the Stock Liquidity with Investor Sentiment as Mediation Variables

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Abstract

The objective of this research is to empirically explore the impact of forward looking statements on the stock liquidity with investor sentiment as mediation variables. The independent variable is the forward looking statement and the dependent variable is stock liquidity and investor sentiment as mediation variables. The analysis technique used is a linear multivariate regression analysis technique. Data span from 2017 to 2022 and covers manufacturing firms listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange. The findings of the research show that the forward looking statement has a significant positive effect on stock liquidity. Forward looking statements have a significant positive effect on investor sentiment. Investor sentiment has a significant positive effect on stock liquidity. Investor sentiment mediates the effect of forward-looking information on stock liquidity. The empirical findings suggest that investor sentiment can play a role as a mediating factor between the disclosure of forward-looking statements and stock liquidity. Therefore, companies should pay special attention to the management of investors' emotions and gain investors' trust by providing clear and accurate information so that they can improve the liquidity of their shares. This article expands and enriches research on forward-looking information disclosure, as well as and is a reference for regulators to develop rules and regulations and regulate forward-looking information disclosure. The association between the extent of disclosure and stock liquidity is still ambiguous. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this study is the first to investigate the impact of forward looking statement on stock liquidity with investor sentiment as meditation.

Keywords: Forward-looking information, Investor sentiment, Stock liquidity.

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Introduction

Financial reporting includes financial statements and non-financial reports (Hidayah et al., 2019). Financial reporting provides information about the current and future status of the company. The information disclosed in annual reports is generally categorized into two types known as mandatory disclosure and voluntary disclosure (Gunawan & Lina, 2015; Afeltra et al., 2024; Biedma López et al., 2024; Kirchsteiger et al., 2024). Mandatory disclosure includes compulsory information obligated by the stock exchange listing requirement, related accounting standards, and statutory requirements, such as, Companies Act (Mohd Ghazali, 2008). Meanwhile, voluntary disclosure includes non-compulsory information that goes beyond the minimum requirements of the capital market regulations (Gunawan & Lina, 2015). The information is disclosed on a voluntary basis by companies based on management discretion. Forward-looking information (FLI) found in the annual report of a company falls under the type of voluntary disclosure (Ah Choi & Joseph, 2020; Call et al., 2024). Forward-looking financial information can be in the form of quantitative, qualitative, financial, and non-financial. The content of a forward-looking statement can include predictions of future events, these events are actually predictions of future economic performance, plans for future operations, etc., which may be misleading if confused with actual events. Information published in the annual report can be classified into two categories: 'backward-looking information' and 'forward-looking information' and it are important to integrate the backward-looking information and the forward-looking information to be provided in the reports (Hussainey, 2004; Kunc et al., 2021). If the information disclosure refers to past financial results, it is called backward-looking. Forward-looking disclosure helps investors and other users evaluate the company's future financial performance by including information containing current plans and future forecasts of the business entity. Such forward-looking disclosure involves financial forecasts such as next year's earnings, expected revenues and anticipated cash flows. In addition to financial information, non-financial information such as risks and uncertainties are also observed in the prospective disclosure. In many cases, forward-looking statements can be identified by words such as "anticipate," "expect," "anticipate," "estimate," "anticipate" or other similar terms. It can be argued that forward-looking information has greater value to stakeholders compared to historical information. For example, forward-looking information is more important than historical information in stock price crash risk prediction (Meng et al, 2017). The results of Keiso and Weygandt (1995) studies show that investors consider forward-looking information in their decision-making process. Bujaki and Zeghal (1999) argued that the publication of forward-looking information in the annual report is useful for reducing the degree of information asymmetry between managers and investors, thereby reducing the firm are cost of external financing. Research on voluntary disclosure focuses on the information role of financial reporting for capital markets (Healy & Palepu, 1995). Studies show that the higher the level of forward-looking information disclosure, the better the stock's liquidity (Li et al., 2023; Abedin et al., 2024). According to agency theory, managers voluntarily disclose new information to reduce information asymmetry and agency cost. In times of poor firm performance, managers provide more information (e.g., forward-looking information) in response to owners' requests for more information to better assess the uncertainty of future cash flows. According to the signaling theory, managers who have good news signal to avoid mergers with managers who have bad news and

voluntarily disclose this information. In addition, managers try to voluntarily disclose bad news (e.g., losses) in order to show their ability and strength to eliminate losses in the future.

Stock liquidity is a function of adverse selection and inefficient stock prices and refers to how easy it is to trade shares without significantly affecting stock prices (Glosten & Milgrom, 1985; Kyle, 1985). Many researchers have focused on the relationship between information disclosure and stock liquidity. Many empirical studies conducted in developed markets argue that voluntary disclosure helps to reduce capital costs and improve stock liquidity. However, in emerging markets, the results of studies are not conclusive: Hassan et al. (2009), Wang et al. (2008) and Chen et al. (2009) show that there is no significant effect of information disclosure neither on firm's value nor on financing cost (debt and equity). Gana and Chameli (2008) found that there is an inverse relationship between stock liquidity and the level of information disclosure. However, Matoussi et al (2004) and Haddad et al. (2009) find a positive relationship between stock liquidity and disclosure level. Notice that the main source of information in these studies is the information publicly and voluntarily disclosed in annual reports (Loukil & Yousfi, 2012). The findings of Edelman and Baker (1990) show that factors such as the number of listed shares, stock price, fundamental factors of the issuer, disclosure of information and market sentiments affect the stock liquidity. Ezat and El-Masry (2008) find a positive significant association between liquidity and corporate disclosure. In contrast, Barako et al. (2006) find no relationship between liquidity and disclosure. Hassanein and Hussainey (2015) suggest that prospective financial information provides information about company performance. However, it does not affect the value of well-performing companies and investors' evaluation of poorly performing companies. Increased levels of disclosure reduce the possibility of information asymmetries, as measured through bid-ask spread, stock liquidity and stock return volatility (Cormier et al., 2010). However, most previous studies have focused on whether specific types of information are disclosed, and although a few researchers have studied forward-looking statement disclosure, they have been limited to the determination of forward-looking information. There is a gap in the research on the impact of information disclosure on stock liquidity. Therefore, is there a relationship between the level of disclosure of forward-looking statements and stock liquidity? Therefore, does the level of disclosure of forward-looking statements affect stock liquidity? If there is a relationship, does the investor sentiment play a mediating role?

The contributions of this study are mainly three points: First, unlike previous studies (Balakrishna et al., 2014) (Dang et al., 2022) (Boubaker et al., 2019) that focused on voluntary disclosure, management tone, and readability of annual reports, this study discusses the relationship between the level of forward-looking statement disclosure and stock liquidity, and expands textual disclosure research by providing new empirical evidence. Second, this study is the first study that considers the relationship between the disclosure of forward-looking statements and stock liquidity by considering the mediating variable of investor sentiments in Iran. Third, due to the fact that the disclosure of the forward-looking statement has an effect on the stock liquidity, it is recommended to the stakeholders to pay more attention to the disclosure of such information, and it has a high degree of validity because it provides the basis for decision-making in the formulation of laws and regulations.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 will be Literature review and hypotheses development, while section 3 will describe the research methods. Section 4 will report the results, and finally, section 5 conclusions discuss the paper.

Literature review and hypothesis development

Managers' incentives to disclose information could be explained through agency and signaling theories (Hassanein & Hussainey, 2015). According to agency theory, managers voluntarily disclose new information to reduce information asymmetry and agency cost. In times of poor firm performance, managers provide more information (e.g., forward-looking information) in response to owners' requests for more information to better assess the uncertainty of future cash flows. According to signaling theory, managers voluntarily disclose information that contains good news to avoid merging with managers who have bad news. In addition, managers voluntarily disclose information that contains bad news to show their ability and power to eliminate future losses. The information disclosed in annual reports plays a crucial role in the functioning of capital markets. Existing theoretical (e.g., Diamond, 1985; Diamond & Verrecchia, 1991) and empirical (e.g., Bhattachary et al., 2013; Brown & Hillegeist, 2007; Heflin et al., 2005; Ng, 2011) literature clearly shows that there is a significant positive and direct relationship between information disclosure and stock liquidity through the reduction of information asymmetry. However, most of the previous studies have focused on the disclosure of quantitative rather than qualitative information in the form of text.

The International Integrated Reporting Framework (hereinafter referred as Framework), drafted and translated by the International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC), strongly emphasizes forward-looking information (Li et al., 2023). Forward-looking statements can be distinguished by words such as "anticipates," "intends," "plans," "seeks," "believes," "continues," "could," "estimates," "expects," "guidance," "may," "might," "outlook," "possibly," "potential," "projects," "projected," "prospects," "should," "will," "would," and comparative references to future periods, but the nonattendance of these words does not mean that an articulation isn't forward-looking. These forward-looking explanations are not ensures of future execution, include or depend on a number of dangers, instabilities, and presumptions that are troublesome to foresee or are past our control, and reflect management's convictions and suspicions based on data accessible at the time the explanations are made. Key terms in FLS include "projections," "guidance," and "earnings forecasts." Forward-looking data is exceedingly requested by different partners in corporate reporting; hence constraining companies to supply such data in their yearly reports (Choi et al., 2022). The costs of disclosing forward-looking information include problems related to the possibility of lawsuits about inaccuracy in forecasting, negative consequences of providing useful information to competitors. At the same time, the benefits of forward-looking information disclosure include the reduction of information asymmetry between managers and investors, efficient allocation of capital, and reduction of financing costs for organizations (Kunc et al., 2021). Forward-looking statement would help investors to assess firms' past and current financial performance, and to predict future earnings (Hussainey et al., 2003). The content of forward-looking information contains the business forecasts of a business institution, which provides useful information to the shareholders to make decisions about the company's future prospects (Alkhatib, 2014). Shareholders frequently have questions

about the future prediction of the company and what is going to happen to the company in the future. The disclosure Forward-looking information can certainly help the users of financial reports to better understand the previous and current performance of a company and thus be able to better predict the future of the company (Liu, 2015). Annual reports play a vital role both for the capital market and in the decision-making process of investors (Barker, 1998; Roberts et al., 2006). However, historical information such as accounting data in annual reports only reflects existing facts that have already occurred or are currently unfolding (Karpoff et al., 2008). Therefore, in a more complex investment environment, it will be very difficult to measure value based on risk and return, and hence in this environment there is an increasing demand from investors for forward-looking information (Huang et al.). Improving the quality of prospective disclosure is an important tool to reduce information asymmetry and reduce adverse selection behavior and increase stock liquidity (Verrecchia, 2001). It not only enhances the informational content in the open market, reducing the likelihood of obtaining excessive returns through information advantage, but also reduces uncertainty in company value. Forward-looking disclosure therefore reduces the information gap arising from being in an information-disadvantaged position and thus increases the willingness of potential investors to trade, thereby aiding in the improvement of stock liquidity. Huang et al. found a significant positive correlation between forward-looking disclosure and a firm's equity liquidity, but is only significant in firms with high levels of internal control situated in regions with well-established legal environments.

Agency theory

Agency theory models put forward by Fama (1969) and Jensen and Meckling (1976), expressing the relationship between the shareholder (as principal) and management (as agent) based on the basic assumption of individual self-interest. Jensen and Meckling (1976) defined the agency relationship as follows: "A contract whereby one or more persons (principals) oblige another person (the agent) to perform services on their behalf, which includes the delegation of decision-making authority to the agent." In this regard, agency theory suggests that the interests of the principal and the agent may not be aligned, as both of them try to maximize their individual interests in any way. Information asymmetry is one of the main factors that initiate agency problems because managers can access more information than shareholders. It is important for stakeholders to reduce information asymmetry by monitoring the agent's opportunistic behavior or by aligning interests between the principal and the agent. Since financial statements are sometimes not enough to reduce the agency problem, agency theory suggests that companies emphasize disclosure in order to reduce conflict between managers and shareholders. As Lundholm and Winkle (2006) stated, voluntary disclosure can be used to reduce the problems of information asymmetry and agency costs (Watson et al., 2002; Barako et al., 2006). Voluntary forward-looking disclosures is believed to reduce the information asymmetry between the principal and the agent (i.e., the shareholder and management in a business environment), thereby eliminating the associated agency problems and costs (Hassanein & Hussainey, 2015; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2018; Seow, 2024).

Signalling theory

Signaling theory is valuable for analyzing disclosure behavior when two parties (organizations or individuals) have different information. Usually, one party (i.e., the sender) must decide whether and how to send information (or signal), and the other party (i.e., the receiver) must decide how to interpret the signal. A signal is a visible action (or structure) that is used to indicate a hidden characteristic (or quality) of the signaler (Sun et al., 2010). The theoretical assumption is that it is desirable for the signaler to send a signal (for example, to indicate the high quality of its products compared to competitors' products). It is believed that signaling to the stakeholders makes the investors attracted to the company and assess the value of the company better and make more favorable decisions (Whiting & Miller, 2008). Corporate disclosure can signal capital markets because managers can use voluntary disclosure to attract new investment and increase their reputation among investors. In this regard, voluntary forward-looking disclosures in particular is a powerful signaling tool in favor of a firm (e.g. strengthening Company image and relationships with various stakeholders, interesting potential investors, reduction of capital costs and reduction of stock volatility) (Elzahar & Hussainey, 2012; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2018; Seow, 2024).

Stakeholder theory

Stakeholder theory includes the relationships between the organization and all the multiple groups that have an interest in it (Roberts, 1992; Gray et al., 1996; Deegan & Blomquist, 2006). Stakeholder theory is based on the idea that the closer a company's relationships are with other stakeholders, the easier it will be to achieve its business goals. Stakeholder theory is often related to the term "accountability" and, from an accounting perspective, accountability refers to the organization's duty to disclose information about its performance, financial status, investments, and compliance in order to support users in making appropriate decisions. An organization must be accountable to all stakeholders within a stakeholder perspective. In this regard, voluntary forward-looking disclosures is increasingly claimed by various stakeholders. It can be estimated that the voluntary forward-looking disclosures reduces the information asymmetry between the company and its shareholders and improves the relationship between them (Menicucci & Paolucci, 2018; Seow, 2024).

Legitimacy theory

Legitimacy theory is concerned with the relationship between the organization and the society in general and assumes that there is a company whose values are consistent with the values of the society in which it operates to be considered as "legitimate" by the various stakeholders of the society (Deegan, 2014). It is believed that voluntary disclosure will be the real means of achieving legitimacy. From the perspective of legitimacy theory, firms should voluntarily disclose information that society expects, because conforming to social expectations can foster continued capital inflows. Agreeing with this view, organizations may use voluntary forward-looking disclosures reporting on a voluntary basis, perhaps in integrated reporting, in order to conform to community expectations or divert community (or media) attention from the negative effects of the organization's core activities (Menicucci & Paolucci, 2018; Seow, 2024).

Forward-looking disclosures may enable investors to form their own expectations about the company's future cash flows and/or returns. In addition, information reduces liquidity costs, thus increasing stock liquidity. Based on the above analysis, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

H₁: There is an association between forward-looking statement disclosure and stock liquidity.

H₂: There is an association between forward-looking statement and investor sentiment.

H₃: There is an association between investor sentiment and stock liquidity.

H₄: Investor sentiment mediator the association between forward-looking statement disclosure and stock liquidity.

Methodology

Data and sample selection

The initial sample consists of firm-year observations in the Tehran stock exchange database for the period 2016–2022. In order to draw a robust conclusion, we apply the following data filters to prior studies: Firstly, we exclude financial firms as they have a capital structure different from other firms. Secondly, a firm must have at least 30 weeks of stock return data in a fiscal year so that it is included in the sample. Thirdly, we remove firm-year observations missing data in estimating variables. As a result, our sample includes 128 firms and 896 firm-year observations. Secondary data (the data that already existed prior to the current needs of the researcher) has been collected for the purpose of this study. Forward-looking statement data were collected manually from the annual reports, and financial and other data were collected from the Tehran Stock Exchange database. In order to mitigate the effects of outliers, all continuous variables are winsorized at the 1st and 99th percentiles.

Variable description

Explained variables

Stock liquidity. Liquidity (or marketability) generally refers to how easily or quickly a security can be bought or sold on a secondary market. One of the advantages of liquid investments is that they can be liquidated easily and without paying a lot of money and in the shortest possible time. A stock's liquidity generally refers to how rapidly shares of a stock can be bought or sold without substantially impacting the stock price. The liquidity of stocks varies greatly based on three primary factors, including their trading volume, bid-ask spread and the efficiency of their respective market. When comparing various stock investment options, it's important to evaluate the stock's liquidity by assessing these three factors. The stock (il) liquidity measure proposed by Amihud (2002) is the most widely-used measure in empirical financial economics. Its key advantage stems from its simple construction, which requires only daily return and dollar volume data that are available for many markets and countries over long periods of time. Many studies show that the Amihud's illiquidity measure performs best in capturing illiquidity among

numerous competing low-frequency liquidity proxies (e.g., Goyenko et al., 2009; Hasbrouck, 2009; Fong et al., 2017). The Amihud (2002) illiquidity ratio (ILLIQ) is defined as the yearly average ratio of daily absolute returns to daily trading volume in monetary terms, and is computed using the following formula (Boubaker et al., 2019):

$$ILLIQ_{i,y} = \frac{1}{D_{i,y}} \sum_{d=1}^{D_{i,y}} \frac{|Return_{i,y,d}|}{Volume_{i,y,d}} \times 10^6 \quad (1)$$

Where $D_{i,y}$ is the number of days for which data are available for stock i in year y . $Return_{i,y,d}$ is the return of stock i on day d in year y . $Volume_{i,y,d}$ is the trading volume of stock i on day d in year y .

Explanatory variables

The level of disclosure of prospective information. To obtain financial data related to the level of forward-looking information, it is necessary to review the annual reports published by companies. The annual report is chosen since it has been traditionally considered to be an influential source of information for investors (Lang & Lundholm, 1993; Marston & Shrivs, 1991). Furthermore, annual report disclosure is highly correlated with other financial communications (Lang & Lundholm, 1993). Regulated sections (financial statements and notes) were excluded from the analysis and only voluntary narrative disclosures in the annual report were examined. Forward-looking disclosure refers to current plans and future forecasts that enable investors and other users to assess a company's future financial performance (Aljifri & Hussainey, 2007). Forward-looking disclosure involves both financial and non-financial information. This paper focuses on specific non-financial information, such as company's development process, Certificates and obtaining environmental standards, Communication with customers and after-sales service, Internet services, the existence of classification of jobs in the organization, Environmental Performance Report. For the forward-looking disclosure variable, a number of ones will be considered for the presence of each of the mentioned terms.

Mediator variables

Investor sentiment. This paper uses the technique developed in Persaud (1996) to create EMSI for a group of companies in a stock market environment. First, the daily yield is calculated for each of the securities. For each security, the average standard deviation of daily returns over the previous five days ("historical volatility") is also calculated for each day of the sample period. Fluctuations and correlation coefficient of Spearman. The rank between the daily return rank for each company and the historical return fluctuation rank for each company are calculated, and the result is multiplied by 100. Therefore, EMSI is calculated as follows (Bandopadhyaya & Jones, 2006):

$$Sent_{i,t} = \frac{\sum(R_{i,r} - \bar{R}_r)(R_{i,v} - \bar{R}_v)}{[\sum(R_{i,r} - \bar{R}_r)^2 \sum(R_{i,v} - \bar{R}_v)^2]^{1/2}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where $R_{i,r}$ and $R_{i,v}$ are the rank of the daily return and the historical volatility for security i , respectively, and R_r and R_v are the population mean return and historical volatility rankings, respectively.

Control variables

In line with previous studies (Urquiza, 2016; Boubaker et al., 2019; Dey et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022; Dang et al., 2022), several variables that are expected to influence stock liquidity were included in the model to control for potentially omitted relationships.

Largest Shareholder Ownership (LSO). The percentage of shareholding of the largest shareholder is measured as the ratio of the number of shares held by the first largest shareholder of the enterprise in the year to the total number of shares.

Institutional Investors Ownership (IO). Shareholding of institutional investors is measured as the ratio of the number of shares held by the enterprise's institutional investors to the total number of shares in that year.

Leverage (Lev). Leverage is measured as the ratio of total debt to total assets.

Firm size (Size). Firm size is measured as the natural logarithm of market value.

Listing age (Age). Firm age is calculated as the number of years that a company has been listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange.

Independent Directors (ID). The percentage of independent directors is measured as the ratio of the number of independent directors to the total number of the enterprise's board of directors for the year.

Stock Return Volatility (SRV). Measured as standard deviation of the daily closing returns.

Statistical models

The researchers performed regression analysis to test the relationships between dependent and independent variables. The researchers analyze panel data, as the use of panel data reduces multicollinearity and reverse causality among the explanatory variables. Thus, improving the efficiency of econometric estimates. The ordinary Least Square (OLS) method is used, after checking the heteroskedasticity (Modified Wald test for groupwise heteroskedasticity), autocorrelation (Wooldridge test for autocorrelation), Multicollinearity (Variance inflation factor test), normality (Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data). Based on literature review, the regression models will be as follows:

To test Hypotheses 1, this study estimated the following model as Model 1:

$$ILLIQ_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FLS_{i,t} + \sum_{i=1}^7 \gamma_i \text{controls variable}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

To test Hypotheses 2, this study estimated the following model as Model 2:

$$SENT_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FLS_{i,t} + \sum_{i=1}^7 \gamma_i \text{controls variable}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

To test Hypotheses 3, this study estimated the following model as Model 3:

$$ILLIQ_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 SENT_{i,t} + \sum_{i=1}^7 \gamma_i \text{controls variable}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

To test Hypotheses 4, this study estimated the following model as Model 4:

$$ILLIQ_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FLS_{i,t} + \beta_2 SENT_{i,t} + \sum_{i=1}^7 \gamma_i \text{controls variable}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

In these equations, the β s are the parameters to be estimated, i is an individual firm, t the year, and $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ the random error. Each equation also included dummy variables for year and industry. We have compared several regression methods for the panel data, including the fixed-effects model (within estimators), the random-effects model, and pooled OLS estimators. Based on the performance of the models, we eventually chose fixed-effects model estimators as our estimation model. We used Stata (statistics software) for statistical analysis.

Experimental results

This section introduces descriptive statistics for the data and samples employed in this study, and report the results of the hypothesis tests.

Descriptive analysis

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for all variables. The results indicate that the average of Amihud illiquidity is -0.058 while the standard deviation is 0.090. For the forward-looking statement variable, the mean is 5.420 and the standard deviation is 1.166, with a minimum of 2.000 and maximum of 7.000. For the investor sentiment variable, the mean is 22.405 and the standard deviation is 14.823, with a minimum of 3.331 and a maximum of 70.527.

Table 1. Descriptive analysis

	Variable	Mean	Median	Max	Min	S.D
1.	<i>ILLIQ</i>	-0.058	-0.003	-0.0005	-0.798	0.090
2.	<i>FLS</i>	5.420	6.000	7.000	2.000	1.166
3.	<i>SENT</i>	22.405	26.106	70.527	3.331	14.823
4.	<i>LSO</i>	0.493	0.503	0.954	0.023	0.202

	Variable	Mean	Median	Max	Min	S.D
5.	<i>IIO</i>	0.666	0.710	0.954	0.059	0.188
6.	<i>Lev</i>	0.524	0.524	1.824	0.031	0.219
7.	<i>Size</i>	15.288	15.081	21.571	11.625	1.538
8.	<i>Age</i>	3.694	4.000	4.262	2.772	0.331
9.	<i>ID</i>	0.607	1.000	1.000	0.200	0.199
10.	<i>SRV</i>	1.249	1.154	3.643	0.093	0.789

Pearson's Correlation between Dependent and Independent Variables

Pearson's correlation matrix shows the correlation between variables (Table 2). Using the correlation coefficient (univariate analysis), the relationships between the variables are tested. There is a positive correlation of 0.092 between Amihud's illiquidity and the forward-looking statement of the company, with a significance of less than 1%, which shows that the forward-looking statement has an effect on the stock liquidity. There is a positive correlation of 0.116 between the forward-looking statement and investor sentiment, with a significance of less than 1%, which shows that the forward-looking statement has an effect on investor sentiment. There is a positive correlation of 0.077 between investor sentiment and Amihud's illiquidity, with a significance of less than 5%, which shows that investor sentiment has an effect on stock liquidity. The correlation matrix results show no sign of multi-collinearity among the independent variables (table 2). As further verification, the tolerance and variable inflation factor (VIF) are examined. Based on Hair et al. (2006), the VIF should be less than 10 and tolerance between 0.1 and 1, as an indication of no multi-collinearity. The VIF values of the independent variables of the sample ranged from less than 10. The tolerance values of all independent variables were more than 0.1 and less than 1 in the samples. The said results confirm the absence of the multi-collinearity problem. All research variables (based on the generalized Dickey-Fuller test) are at the significance level.

Table 2. Pearson correlation matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	VIF
1.	1.000										
2.	0.092***	1.000									1.030
3.	0.077**	0.116***	1.000								1.530
4.	0.044	-0.070**	0.052	1.000							1.730
5.	0.081**	-0.104***	0.206***	0.534***	1.000						1.850
6.	0.096***	-0.051	0.190***	0.220***	0.214***	1.000					1.110
7.	0.002	-0.050	-0.434***	0.020	0.108***	-0.100**	1.000				1.340
8.	-0.033	0.010	-0.138***	-0.176***	-0.117***	-0.123***	0.022	1.000			1.070
9.	-0.078**	-0.010	0.206***	0.066	0.078**	-0.051	-0.136***	-0.037	1.000		1.060
10.	-0.185***	-0.042	-0.310***	-0.036	-0.166***	-0.035	0.015	0.094***	-0.132***	1.000	1.170

Multivariate analysis

The results from panel data regressions examining the influence of forward-looking statements on the stock liquidity on investor sentiment as mediation variables are presented in Table 3. The researchers performed regression analysis to test the relationships between dependent and independent variables. The researchers analyse panel data, as the use of panel data reduces multicollinearity and reverse causality among the explanatory variables. The ordinary Least Square (OLS) method is used, after checking the collinearity, stationary, normality, linearity and serial correlations.

Table 3. Results of regression analyses

Dependent variable	ILLIQ	SENT	ILLIQ	ILLIQ
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
C	-0.17*** (-3.60)	1.18*** (10.95)	-0.14** (-2.44)	-1.92*** (-3.71)
FLS	0.02*** (5.84)	0.01*** (3.81)		0.1*** (2.90)
SENT			0.06** (2.34)	-0.56*** (-5.38)
LSO	-0.01 (-0.69)	-0.10*** (-2.77)	-0.004 (-0.23)	-0.78* (-4.23)
IIO	0.03 (1.53)	0.20*** (5.27)	0.005 (0.24)	0.15 (0.30)
Lev	0.02* (1.70)	0.01 (0.51)	0.02 (1.03)	0.09 (1.37)
Size	0.004** (2.50)	-0.05*** (-12.08)	0.006*** (3.33)	-0.03*** (-6.67)
Age	-0.0003 (-0.05)	-0.09*** (-4.46)	0.004 (0.50)	-0.01 (0.90)
ID	0.04*** (2.83)	-0.09*** (-4.18)	0.04*** (2.93)	0.05*** (2.99)
SRV	0.02*** (4.89)	0.04*** (5.78)	0.03*** (4.78)	0.08*** (4.20)
Industry fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES
R-squared	0.11	0.47	0.07	0.56
Wald statistic	101.12***	310.94***	70.52***	537.52***

Note: *, **, and*** denote 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels, respectively.

Table 3 reports the results from regressing measures of the impact of forward-looking statements on the stock liquidity with investor sentiment as mediation variables, using the models (1)–(4). In the first column, we find that forward-looking statements are significantly positively associated with stock liquidity. This result provides support for the notion that forward-looking statements improve the stock liquidity. The results agree with Li et al. (2023). In the second column, we find that forward-looking statements are significantly and positively associated with investor sentiment. This result provides support for the notion that forward-looking statements improve investor sentiment. The results agree with Li et al. (2023). In the third column, we find that investor sentiment is significantly positively associated with stock liquidity. This result provides support for the notion that investor sentiment improves stock liquidity. Lastly, in the final column, we find that forward-looking statements are significantly positively associated, and

investor sentiment is significantly negatively associated with stock liquidity. Therefore, hypotheses of direct and indirect influence (mediation) are accepted. The results agree with Li et al. (2023). The type of mediation is called “partial mediation” here, because the direct effect is still significant after the mediator is entered into the model. Therefore, disclosure of prospective information has a direct effect on stock liquidity and an indirect effect through the mediating variable of investor sentiments on stock liquidity.

Additional robustness tests

In order to further examine how forward looking statement affects the stock liquidity if investor sentiment is the mediator, the Sobel test has been used. In statistics, the Sobel test is used to test the mediation hypothesis. Michael E. Sobel's work in 1986 and 1983 is the basis of this test, and his application of the delta method. If there is no mediating variable, then the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is a direct influence, whereas if there is a mediating variable, the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is assumed to be an indirect influence. With the presence of a third variable. The variable is intermediate. As a result, when the mediator variable is added to the regression analysis model and placed next to the independent variable, it absorbs some of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, and as a result, the influence of the independent variable becomes greater reduced and remained significantly different from the influence of the mediator variable. The Sobel test is essentially a special t-test that provides a method for determining whether the reduction in the influence of an independent variable, after including a mediator in the model, is a significant reduction and, therefore, whether the mediation effect is statistically significant. According to the model (8) and the obtained coefficients, in this section, the absolute value of the number obtained from the Sobel test is compared with the number 1.96, and the effect of the mediator variable will be significant when the value Z-value is greater than 1.96. In this formula, $Z - Value$ is the Sobel test statistic, a is the effect of the independent variable on the mediator (also known as the ‘a path’), b is the effect of the mediator on the dependent variable. Controlling is the independent variable, S_a is the standard error of a and S_b is the standard error of b . S_a and S_b , are readily available from the statistical output. The Sobel test is calculated as follows.

Sobel test equation:

$$Z - Value = a \times b / \text{SQRT}(b^2 \times s_a^2 + a^2 \times s_b^2) \quad (3)$$

Aroian test equation:

$$Z - Value = a \times b / \text{SQRT}(b^2 \times s_a^2 + a^2 \times s_b^2 + s_a^2 \times s_b^2)$$

Goodman test equation:

$$Z - Value = a \times b / \text{SQRT}(b^2 \times s_a^2 + a^2 \times s_b^2 - s_a^2 \times s_b^2)$$

An illustration of mediation:

a , b , and c' are path coefficients. Values in parentheses are standard errors of those path coefficients.

Description of numbers needed:

a = raw (unstandardized) regression coefficient for the association between IV and mediator.

s_a = standard error of a .

b = raw coefficient for the association between the mediator and the DV (when the IV is also a predictor of the DV).

s_b = standard error of b .

To get numbers:

1. Run a regression analysis with the IV predicting the mediator. This will give a and s_a .
2. Run a regression analysis with the IV and mediator predicting the DV. This will give b and s_b . Note that s_a and s_b should never be negative.

To conduct the Sobel test:

Details can be found in Baron and Kenny (1986), Sobel (1982), Goodman (1960), and MacKinnon et al. (1995). Insert the a , b , s_a , and s_b into the cells below and this program will calculate the critical ratio as a test of whether the indirect effect of the IV on the DV via the mediator is significantly different from zero.

Input:		Test statistic:		Std. Error:	p -value:
a	<input type="text" value="0.0142293"/>	Sobel test:	<input type="text" value="1.99125052"/>	<input type="text" value="0.0004475"/>	<input type="text" value="0.04645335"/>
b	<input type="text" value="0.0626233"/>	Aroian test:	<input type="text" value="1.94315198"/>	<input type="text" value="0.00045858"/>	<input type="text" value="0.0519978"/>
s_a	<input type="text" value="0.0037375"/>	Goodman test:	<input type="text" value="2.04310724"/>	<input type="text" value="0.00043614"/>	<input type="text" value="0.04104182"/>
s_b	<input type="text" value="0.0268047"/>	<input type="button" value="Reset all"/>	<input type="button" value="Calculate"/>		

Alternatively, you can insert t_a and t_b in to the cells below, where t_a and t_b are the t -test statistics for the difference between the a and b coefficients and zero. Results should be identical to the first test, except for errors due to rounding.

Input:		Test statistic:	p-value:
t_a	3.81	Sobel test:	1.99395783
t_b	2.34	Aroian test:	1.94588436
		Goodman test:	2.04577992
			0.04615666
			0.05166863
			0.04077803
Reset all		Calculate	

Given that the absolute values of the numbers obtained by the Sobel test (1.99) are outside the critical regions of +1.96 and -1.96, the significance of the effect of coordinate variables is confirmed.

Conclusion, Implications and Limitations

The research objective of the study is to investigate the impact of forward-looking statements on the stock liquidity with investor sentiment as mediation variables. Based on a sample size of 128 manufacturing firms (896 firm-year observations) listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange from 2016-2022, The positive relationship between forward-looking statements and stock liquidity could be because forward-looking information encompasses substantial informational content, thereby augmenting the incremental efficiency of market information through broader and deeper dissemination of information, mitigating investor information biases or irrational sentiments. The reduction in adverse selection may increase the willingness of uninformed traders to undertake transactions, and thus increase stock liquidity. The company's forward-looking information disclosure would help diminish the information asymmetry between the company and investors, consequently bolstering stock liquidity. The positive relationship between forward statements and investor sentiment suggests that disclosure of forward-looking information not only increases investors' confidence in the future development of enterprises, Rather, it helps to disclose more and more transparent information, thereby reducing information asymmetry. The positive relationship between investor sentiment and stock liquidity could be because investor sentiment can further amplify stock volatility by aggravating the level of information asymmetry. The analysis shows that the level of forward-looking statement disclosure affects the stock's liquidity through investors' sentiments. Consistent with previous studies (Li et al., 2023), this study concludes that there is a significant relationship between forward-looking statements on the stock liquidity.

The findings of this study have policy and practical implications for regulators, managers and investors. This study helps information users to be more aware of the forward-looking statements of companies and analysis it better. It helps the decision-making authorities and regulators to improve the rules and regulations related to the disclosure of forward-looking information and to strengthen the supervision of the disclosure of forward-looking information. It reminds the management to pay more attention to the disclosure of forward-looking information. This study contributes to the forward-looking information literature and provides an important addition to the evidence by examining the link between forward-looking statements on the stock liquidity with investor sentiment as mediation variables for privatized companies in an emerging

market. And complements earlier studies on the effects of forward-looking statements on stock liquidity.

However, this study has some limitations that provide interesting opportunities for further research. Firstly, since the estimation of forward-looking statements is relatively clear and repeatable, it is suggested to examine broader measures of forward-looking statements as additional measures of companies' disclosure approaches. We have examined one of the features of financial reporting in our study. Future work could examine additional features of financial reporting to gain more insight into how managerial internal resource allocation decisions are made, as well as the consequences of these decisions for the Stock liquidity. Secondly, the sample size in this study was limited to manufacturing companies listed to the Tehran Stock Exchange. Future studies can be extended to non-listed companies and compare these two categories and a longer period of years could be covered to have a true reflection on the issue. Finally, in this study, only one proxy is used for the stock liquidity, future studies could also examine other liquidity indicators or use investor sentiments as a moderating variable. Another limitation is researcher subjectivity in applying manual content analysis.

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